

SOCIAL JUSTICE IN DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF SOCIAL PROTECTION AT THE NEW STAGE OF UZBEKISTAN'S DEVELOPMENT

Hamroev Saidjon Sanoevich

Dean of the Faculty of Pedagogy and Social Sciences

Pedagogical Institute of Bukhara State University,

Bukhara, Uzbekistan

ss9337@mail.ru

Annotation. In today's Uzbekistan, great practical work is being carried out in order to fundamentally improve the establishment of the state and civil society, to ensure the priority of law and justice, to liberalize the economy, and to develop the social sphere in all aspects. In this article, it has been analyzed that the main goal of Uzbekistan is to establish the principles of social justice in all spheres of society's life in democratic processes.

Keywords: social justice, freedom, development, COVID-19, poverty, social policy, business, employed, strategy

In Uzbekistan, the principle of social justice through social support of citizens is taking place in the conditions and in the space of freedom, legislation and democracy in all spheres of social life in the context of socio-economic and political processes.

President Shavkat Mirziyoev states that «It is this historical necessity and the objective social political process that are creating extremely important foundations for the creation and implementation of strategic principles and practical activity programs that determine the current development and prospects of Uzbekistan in all areas»[1].

Today, the principle of social justice in Uzbekistan covers the political, economic, and spiritual spheres of society. It is an important factor in the liberation

of the state and society, because we are building not just a democratic society, but a just democratic society.

At the same time, COVID-19, which threatened the whole world, including our Uzbekistan, was a great experience and lesson for everyone. This gave an opportunity to conclude on the future priority tasks of the state policy to reduce poverty in the country. All participants were once again convinced of the importance of continuous investment in human capital, education and health system development, and the importance of coping with the unexpected.

In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his address at the 75th and 76th sessions of the UN General Assembly, emphasized the need to unite global efforts in the fight against poverty, especially during the pandemic and after. Basically, in the address of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, the fight against poverty was defined as a priority task in the policy of economic development.

Currently in the world, with this policy, reducing the level of poverty, improving people's lifestyle and living well-being, the issues raised as a priority of any state policy are included in the speeches of the leaders of the countries and on the agenda of relevant international organizations.

In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated that «Poverty reduction means the implementation of a comprehensive economic and social policy to awaken the spirit of entrepreneurship in the population, to fully realize the inner strength and potential of a person, and to create new jobs»[2].

Nowadays, the great saying «Uzbekistan is a social state» is coming to the fore. This will also be strengthened in the country's Constitution, which is scheduled to be amended in the near future. Based on this principle, it will be a factor for us to advance to the stage of development of the new Uzbekistan in the country. There are a few basics in this regard. First of all, it is necessary to study the impact of the

concept of the social state on the way of living and improving the life of ordinary people, and to form the understanding of people and ourselves about it.

As stated by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his speech at the meeting with the members of the Constitutional Commission, which is called «the main goal of our constitutional reforms is to ensure human dignity and the interests of the people in practice», the social state creates decent living conditions for every person based on the principles of social equality and justice. It is a model of the state that conducts an effective policy of reducing social differences and helping the needy [3].

The welfare state defines the minimum amount of all consumer goods that those in need need to improve their lifestyle, house and live. It envisages the provision of employment for every citizen to lead a decent life, adequate wages, safe working conditions and reduction of poverty. It is worth noting that in the social state, every person is taken into account, the problems related to them cannot be left alone. Because everything will be under the control of the social state.

In the period of new development in Uzbekistan, based on the idea of «For human dignity», new systems such as «Iron Notebook», «Women's Notebook», «Youth Notebook» have been created and active efforts are being made to support citizens in need of social protection. Within the framework of these programs, practical work was done in the country to increase the income of the population and ensure their employment, to train the unemployed population, especially the youth, in the profession, to help them start their business activities, and to provide material and social support.

In particular, during the past period, 651,000 families included in the «Iron Notebook» were removed from the «Iron Notebook» by ensuring the employment of 705,200 unemployed people of more than 2.7 million of their members. Also, measures were taken to create a permanent source of income for the families

included in the register. In particular, 96,600 citizens have been permanently employed, 34,700 citizens have started business activities. Also, 16,500 citizens were trained in the profession.

In addition, regular medical, psychological and legal services are provided to the families included in the register. In particular, 13.6 thousand family members (93.8 percent) of 14.5 thousand families in need of medical protection underwent medical examinations.

So far, 279.7 billion soums of financial assistance have been provided to 293.2 thousand families included in the «Iron Notebook» from the funds of the «Sakhavat va Komak» fund [4].

No international document on poverty has been adopted, but there is a UN definition of who is considered poor. According to it, «Poverty is invisible when a person does not have choices and opportunities throughout his life, there are obstacles to full participation in society, he can feed and clothe his family, receive education and treatment, he is helpless in the face of dangers, and there is a lack of opportunities to provide work».

In general, many definitions and meanings given to the concept of poverty can be summed up as follows. Poverty is a lack of income and security of life for every citizen to lead a full and decent life for himself and his family.

In the United States in 2010, the number of poor people was 46 million, which was 15.1 percent of the total population. By 2021, the poverty rate will be 7.7 percent [5].

In a word, the causes of poverty affect human potential and the development of producers in Uzbekistan, as well as the economic activity of the people.

The «New Uzbekistan» development strategy for 2022-2026 was approved in the country, and active practical work in this regard has begun. This, in turn, is based on the principle of «For the honor and dignity of man». The main task of the

development of the economy of Uzbekistan is to reduce the level of poverty by half by 2026 in the 85th goal of the development strategy [6].

In particular, it is planned to increase the level of the gross domestic product per capita from the current 2000 US dollars to 2800 US dollars by 2026. This will pave the way for entry into the upper group of middle-income countries by 2030. On the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, one of the new systems for improving the management system from the economic side - the institute of khokim (the governor) assistants was introduced and attached to each neighborhood. The purpose of this initiative is to provide financial assistance to the entrepreneurship of the population, to further improve the mechanisms of ensuring their employment and to reduce the level of poverty.

It is worth noting that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev defined the problem of poverty elimination in the country as a strategic task. To solve this problem, separate institutions were established to fight against poverty in the country. In particular, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation was established and determined the state policy on fighting against poverty. In addition, the Ministry of Mahalla and Family Support was established in order to support low-income families in need of social protection. This ministry acts as a responsible state body coordinating the activities of citizens' self-governance bodies, and ensures the improvement of the quality and efficiency of providing targeted assistance to low-income and needy families in the regions. Ensuring control, transparency and addressability will be the priority in allocating these financial aids.

A strong social policy means that public institutions allocate social resources in favor of the disadvantaged and vulnerable members of society. In recent years, the work carried out in Uzbekistan in this regard has been highly appreciated by the world community. In a word, it can be noted that the work carried out in this regard in the country was chosen as a model of public policy that corresponds to the concept of social justice.

In conclusion, it can be said that poverty alleviation in Uzbekistan should be carried out only by increasing the effectiveness of social protection through specific and systematic approaches.

Especially in the country in recent years, significant work has been done in other areas that help to eliminate poverty. In particular, subsidies were allocated for the development of entrepreneurship through support, creation of new jobs in them, development of rural areas and agriculture. In addition, we can take as an example the processes of improving the infrastructure of rural areas through modern design, improving health care, education and upbringing.

Therefore, the positive changes in the ongoing reforms in this regard are considered an important part of Uzbekistan's long-term planned poverty reduction program.

REFERENCES:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2021 457-p.
2. Newspaper: Yangi O'zbekiston, Saturday, January 25, 2020 No 1(1)
3. Newspaper: Yangi O'zbekiston, Tuesday, June 21, 2022, No 122 (644).
4. Newspaper: Buxoronoma, Wednesday, June 1, 2022. No. 41
5. *Dylan Matthews*. [The big drop in American poverty during the pandemic, explained](#) (angl.). *Vox* (11 avgusta 2021).
6. Newspaper: Xalq so'zi, February 1, 2022, Tuesday 23 No (8085)
7. Sobirovich T. B. The implementation of human indicator reforms in Uzbekistan //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – C. 197-202.
8. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 1. – C. 334-338.

9. Sobirovich T. B. National Principles of Democracy in Uzbekistan //Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS). – 2021. – T. 5. – №. 3. – C. 131-135.

10. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of Renewal of National Spirituality of Uzbekistan //International Journal on Integrated Education. – 2020. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 122-126.

11. Sobirovich T. B., Murodogli I. S. The strategy for the implementation of the modern governance system in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 5. – C. 741-748.